

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI TRIESTE

OPEN SCIENCE & FAIR DATA COURSE

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PHD PROJECT

Prediction of key properties of molecular (nano)systems for biological and industrial application through HPC-based techniques and experimental validation

MY (NEW) DEFINITION OF OPEN SCIENCE

“Transparency”

- A system to conduct and benefit responsible and trusted research, revolutionizing the access and generation of data and knowledge, preferring the dialogue with other systems and engaging societal actors, in order to develop a research community based on transparency and knowledge-oriented. *(OS as a system, FAIR management, OA policy, re-use of data, open educational resources)*
- Must rethink the economic business model of journals with a view to fully achieve the OS goals. *(fundings, OA paths)*

WHAT I CAN DO NOW

Be more aware of the policy of publishing

- Previous articles: 2 article in OA, 2 not
- Check the policies using DOAJ, Sherpa Romeo or Journal Checker tool (e.g. next on Spectrochimica Acta → not present in DAOJ, OA pathway with fee)
- Talk more consciously with my supervisor about where to publish and go open

Share contents with a cc using creativecommons.org (like this ppt)

Naming file system and use only standard formats

- All data in csv format
- Include the date in analysis excel name, in the format:
YYYYMMDD_protein_conc_system_analysis_testnumber

WHAT I CAN DO IN THE NEXT PROJECT

DMP

- Data organization: based on experiment type
- Storage solution: in my/laboratory pc + online repository + offline backup device
- Dataset description: wavelength/intensity (spectroscopy) or time/heat (calorimetry) in csv
- Metadata: spectroscopy instrumentations in excel format → better with a xml standard?

ELN

- Electronic Lab Notebook
- To document your experiments and data in a structured, searchable manner
- e.g. LabArchives

Protocol

- Check and publish on Protocols exchange tool
- e.g. HSA esterase activity assay